

Dynamic Range Considerations When Designing PC Sound Card Based Audiometric Systems to Test Human Hearing

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Abstract—An investigation into maximizing the dynamic range of a PC sound card based audiometric test system is presented. Two principle sound paths are characterized: a) the analog line input, and, b) internal waveform conversion from digital formats into analog signals. Each signal path's electrical performance and overall dynamic range is measured using audio harmonic distortion analysis and frequency spectrum analysis tools. Recommendations are made for proper combinations of signal amplitude and mixer attenuation settings to maximize overall system dynamic range. This work could be useful for scientists using PC sound card based systems for psycho-acoustic testing purposes or for those using similar systems attempting to test the full range of human hearing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Research investigating human hearing often requires the creation of custom acoustic stimulus generation instrumentation based upon PC sound systems for various reasons, among them being: 1) the sound quality of PC sound systems can be very good, and 2) many PC software tools are available which directly support creation, editing, and presentation of acoustic stimuli in the testing environment. A typical configuration is shown and described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PC-based sound systems consist of a “sound card” device connected to a PC with software applications passing waveform data and mixing volume information to the card over a digital interface. Sound card signal paths usually include: 1) Line Input for external analog signal sources, and, 2) internal digital waveform generators. Both signal paths are combined and made available at the Line Output. Depending on acoustic transducer selection, an external power amplifier might be necessary to maintain signal quality or raise acoustic amplitude.

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The *dynamic range*, usually expressed in decibels (dB), is defined as the ratio between the smallest and largest signal amplitudes passed by the system with adequate *sound quality* which is defined as freedom from signal distortion and audible *artifacts*, i.e., unwanted signals. The system dynamic range and signal quality requirements vary depending on the research application. Psycho-acoustical and cognitive-neural application areas might only require “comfortable listening levels” or a dynamic range of 30dB, while testing the full range of human auditory thresholds can require, depending on the acoustic transducer frequency response, a dynamic range of 120dB with calibrated stimulus volume levels at 1dB resolution. The discussion in this paper will primarily be focused on *electrical* dynamic range, measured at the line output of the sound card and referenced to a standard voltage such as 1VRMS (0dBV) or 0.775VRMS (0dBu), as compared to an *acoustical* dynamic range of sound pressure level (SPL). SPL dB units are referenced to the threshold of hearing, 20uPa, and measured using a microphone at the acoustic transducer output. Within the transducer linear performance region, generally an electrical dB ratio maps directly to an acoustical dB SPL ratio (i.e. $\Delta 10\text{dBV} = \Delta 10\text{dB SPL}$). Introductory materials on audio engineering and psycho-acoustical topics referred to in this paper are readily available [1] and [2]. It is assumed the reader is familiar with basic electrical signal measurement and analysis techniques such as the total harmonic distortion (THD) and amplitude v. frequency spectrum analysis via the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)[3]

A functional view of the principal internal sound card (SC) signal path components is shown in Figure 2. The Line Input signal passes through an amplifier and terminates in a variable resistor, Line-in. The SC contains a Wave Player subsystem which converts computer generated, digitally-encoded waveforms to analog signals whose output also passes to a variable resistor, Wave-in. The resistors act as volume controls passing adjustable signal amplitudes to a summing amplifier which combines and passes both signals (referred to as *mixing*) to the Line-out variable resistor. The variable resistors or volume controls (also commonly called *attenuators* since they usually only reduce signal amplitude), are controlled by the SC Mixer Control subsystem. The SC Waveform Control circuitry manages the digital to analog conversion process. SC digital interfaces to the PC software platform include the internal PCI bus, and external USB and Firewire peripheral interface

Figure 2. Functional view of typical sound card internal circuitry for signal generation, combining, and level setting. PC software applications send: 1) waveform data to Waveform Control which manages digital to analog signal conversions, and, 2) messages to the Mixer Control to adjust Line-in, Wave-in, and Line-out signal levels.

standards. PC software applications are provided access to the internal SC Waveform and Mixer Controls via SC driver software, operating system sound system software, and various commercial and custom sound software libraries.

While SC selection and market surveying is beyond the scope of this paper, in general, to consider testing human hearing, a SC with 24 bit accuracy, 48kHz sample rate (DVD quality), and balanced-line signal input/output lines is necessary with example products given below¹. In application areas not requiring extended dynamic range and absolute signal quality, SC devices of lesser performance quality and possibly lower cost, might be applied. In either case, assuming modern SC devices have stable electrical performance, the most common control parameters affecting dynamic range and signal quality include the signal path mixing levels and the external analog and internal digital waveform characteristics. Holding the SC quality constant, we looked at the effect of varying external and internal signal amplitudes in combination with varied mixing levels on system dynamic range and signal quality using the following methods.

II. METHODS

A series of dynamic range and signal quality electrical measurements were taken on a PC system equipped with a USB SC as shown in Figure 3. The SC line-in and wave-in signal paths were considered independently. Audio measurements were made at line-out while manually varying signal generator and waveform amplitudes from maximum to useable minimum in 10dB steps (actual step

¹ Card Deluxe, internal PCI bus, Digital Audio Labs, Chanhassen, MN, USA; Lynx Two, internal PCI bus, Lynx Studio Technology, Inc., Cost Mesa CA, USA; Edirol UA-101, external USB bus, Roland Corporation, Shizuoka City, Shizuoka, Japan.

sizes when detecting human response to signals could be smaller). For each signal path, the sequencing effect of

Figure 3. System configuration as implemented consists of signal generator feeding channel 3 of a USB-based sound card with channel 3 output routed to the audio analyzer. Software running on the PC is used to generate and control the sound card waveform generator and to control signal mixing levels.

varying signal amplitude v. signal mixing level of a 997Hz² sine wave[4] was recorded.

The line-in amplitude was adjusted by an ATS-2 provided software application. The wave-in digital waveforms with amplitudes ranging from 0dBV (0.99VRMS) to -60dBV (1.0mVRMS) were created as an Audacity® project. The built-in Windows 7® PC sound mixing application was used to manually adjust SC line-in, wave-in, and line-out levels. In real-world applications, operating system or SC libraries often programmatically control mixing levels.

The auto-ranging audio analyzer input bandwidth was set to 22-20kHz. At the upper amplitude ranges, standard total harmonic distortion plus noise (THD+N) was measured as both relative ratio (%) and absolute amplitude (uV) as recommended for noise-limited devices as in [5]. For lower fundamental signal amplitude levels, a 64 average, Equiripple® windowed, 8192 point FFT spectral analysis was recorded. To maximize the signal to noise ratio on the SC, the +4dBu (1.227VRMS) range was selected. ATS-2 key specs are given in³.

III. RESULTS

The measurement results for the line-in and wave-in signal paths are presented in Tables I, II and III, IV respectively. The results table format, while appearing redundant, exposes performance subtleties important to proper system design. Tables I and III demonstrate the impact of first varying signal source amplitude then varying mixing level and Tables II and IV contain varying mixing level followed by varying amplitude results. Line In and Line Out are in mixer slider positional units, all other values, including graph vertical axis are in dBu, rounded to

² Sine wave 997Hz is an industry standard measurement frequency when working with standard sampling frequencies of 44.1kHz and 48kHz.

³ ATS-2 signal generator THD+N and audio analyzer residual THD+N: $\leq (0.0009\% [-101\text{dB}] + 1.6\text{uV})$.

1dBu resolution, with * values at 2dBu resolution, and except where noted. Attenuation step sizes cannot be assumed under mixing control since step sizes generally widen at reduced levels. Audio analyzer measured results are presented until THD+N % measurements are meaningless due to small fundamental frequency amplitudes, thereafter averaged FFT measurement results are presented until the signal is about 10dB above the noise floor (minimum usable amplitude). Generally, the authors consider moderate to high level pure tone stimuli with THD+N figures greater than 2% and low level signals with fundamental frequency amplitudes less than 10dB greater than the noise floor or harmonic frequency amplitudes to be unsuitable for threshold testing. When at the end of either the usable attenuation or amplitude series of settings, the FFT spectrum indicates signal quality as it displays the device noise floor along with any non-random artifacts present in the signal which could reduce signal quality. The dynamic range of each configuration equals the top-most level minus the lowest level.

TABLE I
Line-in, Line-out Path, Amplitude then Attenuation Sequence

Level	Gen Level	Line In	Line Out	THD+N %	THD+N uV	
<i>Audio Analyzer Measurements</i>						
+4	+4	100	100	0.006	69	
0	0	100	100	0.007	52	
-10	-10	100	100	0.020	48	
-20	-20	100	100	0.064	48	
-30	-30	100	100	0.208	48	
-40	-40	100	100	0.671	48	
-50	-50	100	100	2.070	48	
-60	-60	100	100	6.620	48	
<i>FFT Analyzer Measurements</i>						
				Noise Floor	1 st Even	1 st Odd
-50	-50	100	100	-113	-113	-113
-60	-60	100	100	-113	-112	-113
-70	-70	100	100	-114	-112	-114
-80	-80	100	100	-114	-113	-114
-90	-90	100	100	-114	-113	-112
-100	-100	100	100	-114	-113	-113
-110	-110	100	100	-114	-114	-113
-60	-50	32	100	-118	-113	-112
-70	-50	10	100	-119	-112	-112
-80	-50	3	100	-120	-114	-109
-90	-50	1	100	-120	-118	-117
-100	-50	1	70	-120	-118	-117
-110	-50	1	31	-121	-120	-116

IV. DISCUSSION

Overall, with either line-in or wave-in signals, the greatest dynamic range, quietest (lowest noise floor

measurement), and best signal quality (least 1st odd and even harmonic amplitudes) occur by first applying attenuation, then reducing signal amplitude. This is because mixer volume controls attenuate both fundamental frequency and noise components of the signal, yielding lower THD+N values and improved noise floor, ultimately resulting in increased dynamic range. The precise cross over point between attenuation and amplitude settings will be application dependent and probably device dependent. Attenuation instabilities, possibly interacting with slider direction motion, and often occurring at * levels were experienced at particularly low mixer level settings. Authors consider this SC and possibly operating system driver related since the Lynx® TwoB with its custom mixing application and driver has not demonstrated these issues. Disregarding the attenuation instabilities, by varying attenuation followed by varying amplitude, the dynamic range shown in Table IV approaches 130dB with signal averaging which is nearly 10dB better the Table III wave-in results.

TABLE II
Line-in, Line-out Path, Attenuation then Amplitude Sequence

Level	Amp dBV	Line In	Line Out	THD+N%	THD+N uV	
<i>Audio Analyzer Measurements</i>						
+4	+4	100	100	0.006	68	
0	+4	63	100	0.006	48	
-10	+4	20	100	0.012	28	
-20	+4	7	100	0.036	26	
-30	+4	2	100	0.111	25	
-40	+4	1	59	0.322	25	
-50	+4	1	30	0.534	25	
-60*	+4	1	2	3.910	24	
<i>FFT Analyzer Measurements</i>						
				Noise Floor	1 st Even	1 st Odd
-50	+4	1	30	-120	-115	-117
-60	-6	1	30	-120	-113	-116
-70	-16	1	30	-120	-113	-118
-80	-26	1	30	-120	-110	-110
-90*	-36	1	30	-120	-120	-116
-100*	-46	1	30	-120	-116	-120
-110*	-56	1	30	-120	-120	-120

This amount of dynamic range if coupled properly to an acoustic transducer with flat frequency response (e.g. ±5dB) might be useable for human testing down to, and possibly below, the threshold of hearing (0dB SPL). The other configuration combinations tested, could be applied but with more difficulty to human hearing testing.

The reliable SC mixer attenuation range for either signal path looks to be around 50-55dB. From Table III, it appears digital waveform amplitude of -60dBV might be the bottom of useable range. Amplitudes below this level exercise a decreasing number of quantization bits resulting in reduced dynamic range of the waveform generator as a signal source (theoretically, each bit = ~6dB of dynamic range [6]). For any configuration, it can be seen even a small increase in attenuation from minimum can immediately improve signal quality as THD+N drops. When not using pure tone stimuli, the peak amplitudes of sound content must also be considered to avoid distortion due to clipping of the signal.

Depending on the application field and dynamic range requirements, an adequate acoustic system might be able to be implemented using just the amplitude or attenuator volume control methods which would simplify software development and calibration methods.

TABLE III

Wave-in, Line-out Path, Amplitude then Attenuation Sequence

Level	Amp dBV	Wave In	Line Out	THD+N %	THD+N uV	
<i>Audio Analyzer Measurements</i>						
+15	0	100	100	0.008	378	
+5	-10	100	100	0.007	100	
-5	-20	100	100	0.021	95	
-15	-30	100	100	0.066	95	
-25	-40	100	100	0.207	95	
-35	-50	100	100	0.667	94	
-45	-60	100	100	2.110	94	
<i>FFT Analyzer Measurements</i>						
				Noise Floor	1 st Even	1 st Odd
-35	-50	100	100	-110	-110	-88
-45	-50	32	100	-114	-114	-97
-55	-50	10	100	-114	-108	-108
-65	-50	3	100	-114	-111	-112
-75	-50	1	100	-114	-111	-113
-85	-50	1	52	-118	-118	-115
-95	-50	1	30	-120	-120	-119
-105	-50	1	15	-120	-117	-117

V. CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this paper was to investigate how to maximize the dynamic range of a PC sound system while maintaining signal quality. The material reported here could be useful to the scientist considering, designing, implementing, or calibrating a SC based audiometric system or could help understand how operational parameters of sound cards can affect overall system audiometric performance.

The line-in and wave-in signal paths of a particular PC sound card were analyzed for evaluation in building custom

audiometric test systems capable of testing human hearing. Our measurements show that by manipulating signal source amplitudes and mixer attenuation settings a system can be created with wide dynamic range while maintaining signal quality. It was also learned there could be mixing level instabilities at the very lowest volume settings. Depending on the frequency response characteristics of the acoustic transducer, by proper selection of signal generator levels and sound card mixing controls, audiometric-type systems with dynamic range capabilities similar to the human ear can be created that are suitable for testing human audiometric thresholds. However, building custom PC based sound systems to test the full range of human hearing could be dependent of the selection of the sound card. Careful attention to sound card selection is advised since using other sound cards may result in different findings.

TABLE IV

Wave-in, Line-out Path, Attenuation then Amplitude Sequence

Level	Amp dBV	Wave In	Line Out	THD+N %	THD+N uV	
<i>Audio Analyzer Measurements</i>						
+15	0	100	100	0.008	370	
+5	0	32	100	0.004	60	
-5	0	10	100	0.010	47	
-15	0	3	100	0.033	45	
-25	0	1	100	0.100	45	
-35	0	1	20	0.180	24	
-45	0	1	5	0.532	26	
-55	0	1	1	1.700	25	
<i>FFT Analyzer Measurements</i>						
				Noise Floor	1 st Even	1 st Odd
-45	0	1	5	-122	-119	-119
-55	0	1	1	-120	-109	-111
-65	-10	1	1	-120	-116	-118
-75	-20	1	1	-120	-112	-115
-85*	-30	1	1	-120	-120	-113
-95*	-40	1	1	-120	-118	-118
-105*	-50	1	1	-120	-118	-120
-115*	-60	1	1	-120	-120	-120

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